

Notes

Synthesis of New Organometallic Compounds as Potential Pesticides : Part 1.

GEETA BAIJAL* and A. N. DEY †

Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur.

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VANDERKERK and Luijten have synthesized aliphatic tin compounds which have marked bacteriotoxic and fungitoxic properties. In view of this we have synthesised organo mercury and tin esters from aliphatic acids present in coconut oil by condensation reaction with substituted cresols. The synthetic procedure of Mehrotra and Dey² was adopted and *o*, *m* and *p* cresols were coupled with caprylic, capric, lauric, myristic, palmitic and stearic acids as well as acetic, propionic and butyric acid through their intermediary acid chlorides formed by treating them with thionyl chloride. The synthetic route can be represented as

The structure of individual components was verified^{3,4} through gravimetric estimation of tin and mercury. The synthetic route of this series was further confirmed by infrared and elemental analysis on few representative compounds. The sharp bands were obtained at

* Present address : Department of Petroleum Technology, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad.

† Deceased.

3000 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} , 840 cm^{-1} and 800 cm^{-1} , confirming the existence of $-CH$, $-C-$ and *p*-substituted phenyl ring in the molecule. The broad band at 1460 cm^{-1} is due to $-CH_2$, CH_3 and phenyl ring and band at 1030 cm^{-1} confirms the C-O-C linkage in the molecule. The calculated and experimental values of C, H, Mercury and tin of few compounds are given in Table 1. (Please see p. 94)

Results and Discussion

The pesticidal properties are tested⁵ against three fungi namely *Aspergillus niger* (A. N.), *Chetomium globossum* (CG) and *Rhizoctonia solani* (R. S.) and two bacteria namely, *Escherichia coli* (E. C.) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (S. A.). The activity of these compounds is also compared against standard pesticide zineb (zinc ethylene bisdithiocarbamate).

The fungicidal activity are best exhibited in mercurated esters based on caprylic, capric and lauric acid. Individually the cresyl esters of caprylic, capric and lauric are more active than of esters prepared from myristic, palmitic and stearic acids.

In the tin series too cresyl esters developed on caprylic, lauric and capric acids have shown marked pesticidal properties although in these fungicidal properties are more pronounced specially from their meta substituents.

It would thus be evident that between the mercury and tin compounds the former have better pesticidal characters. It was also clear that acids present in coconut oil impart remarkable pesticidal properties to mercury and tin cresyl esters.

References

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SYNTHESIZED SUBSTITUTED CRESYL ESTERS

Sl. No. of compound	ORTHO CRESOL				META CRESOL				PARA CRESOL				
	Mercury-compound		Tin-compound		Mercury-compound		Tin-compound		Mercury-compound		Tin-compound		
	MP°C and yield%	Hg% found	MP°C and Yield% and colour	Sn% found	C,H% found	MP°C and yield	H% found	MP°C yield% and colour	Sn% found	C,H% found	H% calcd	Hg% calcd	Sn% calcd
1. CH ₃ (CH ₃) ₆	135;50	43.0	230(d); 38,DY	30.5	46.2 5.3	140; 52	42.8	198; 36 DY	30.4				
2. CH ₃ (CH ₃) ₁₃	143;39	34.0	210;43 F	24.6		106; 52	33.9	233 (d); 41, DF	24.7	53.4 6.8			
3. CH ₃ (CH ₃) ₁₄	148;42	32.9	248(d); 39Y	23.1		117; 35	33.0	213; 37 Y	23.2	55.1 7.2			
4. CH ₃ (CH ₃) ₃	115;39	45.3	215; 32 L.M.	35.1	39.7 3.6	125; 42	45.4	220(d); 38, M	35.3				
						120; 48	43.1	189 (d); 40, Y	30.6	46.5 5.2	5.4	43.4	30.8
						112; 38	34.2	202; 40 DF	24.8	53.5	7.01	34.5	25.0
						115; 36	32.8	168(d); 35, Y	23.1	55.3	7.4	33.1	23.6
						127; 38	45.6	205.48 M	35.2	39.9 3.7	3.9	45.8	35.7

Continued below

M=Maroon, B=Brown, Y=Yellow, F=Fawn, G=Grey, D=Dark and L=Light, d = decompose.